

The Changing of Global Marketing Trend; Indian National Income – A Long Term Analysis

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Nandhini, K. “The Changing of Global Marketing Trend; Indian National Income – A Long Term Analysis.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 106–111.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461450>

K.Nandhini

II-M.Com, Morappur Kongu College of Arts and Science, Morappur

Abstract

India is on a country of diverse nature in almost areas. The dualism is the highest at many levels. It is the place for the live on more than 127 crore people. Global marketing is “Marketing on the worldwide scale reconciling or taking commercial advantage of on global operational differences, similarities and opportunities to meet those global objectives.”

Global marketing is also their field of study in general business management to provide valuable products, solutions and then services to customers locally, nationally, internationally and worldwide.

International marketing is the export, franchising, joint venture or full direct entry of an organization’s product or services into another country. This can be achieved by their exporting a company’s product to another location, entry through a joint venture with another firm in the target country or foreign direct investment into the target country. The development of marketing mix for that country is then required - international marketing. It can be as straight forward as using existing marketing strategies, mix and tools for export on the one side, to a complex relationship strategy including localization, local product offerings, pricing, production and the distribution to more than one and distribution with customized promotions, offers, website, social sector media and leadership. Internationalization and global marketing meet the needs of selected foreign countries where a company’s value can be exported and there is inter-firm and firm learning, optimization and efficiency in economies of scale and scope.

Introduction

A firm does not need to export or enter all world markets to be considered an international marketer. According to American Marketing Association (AMA) “International marketing is the multinational process of planning and then executing the conception, pricing, promotion and distribution of ideas, goods and services to create exchanges that satisfy individual and organizations goals.”

Emerging Service Sector in on Marketing Level

The service sector marketing was an emerging leader in business. The requires to exports in business and commerce for leading to the country. It could add on national income which will be substance for Indian economic grow the thing. The contribution of the agriculture sector is coming down in that recent past marketing. This suggestion that we have to the place more emphasis on that agribusiness marketing management. The role of all the sector need not be under estimated as each one of the contributed to the business development and the increase in the national income of our mother, India.

World Wide Competition

One of the product categories in which that global competition is on easy to track in the U.S is on automotive sales. The increasing intensity of competition in global markets is a challenge facing companies at all stages of development in the international markets. As markets open up and become more than integrated, the pace of change accelerates, technology shrinks distances between the markets and reduces in scale advantages of large firms, new sources of competition emerge, and competitive pressures mount at all levels of the organization.

Also, the threat of competition from the companies in countries such as India, China, Malaysia, Brazil is on the rise, as their own domestic markets trend are opening up to foreign competition, stimulating awareness of international market opportunities and of the need to be internationally competitive. Companies which are previously focused on the protected domestic markets are entering into markets in other countries, creating new sources of competition, often to that targeted to price-sensitive market segments. Not only is competition intensifying for all firms that regardless of their degree of global market involvement, but the basis for competition is changing. Competition continues to be market-based and ultimately relies on delivering superior value to the consumers. However, success in global markets depends on that knowledge accumulation and deployment. Today, more and more marketing companies specialize in translating products from one country to another.

Evaluation of Global Marketing

Global marketing is not on revolutionary shift; it is an evolutionary process. While the following does not apply to all companies, it does apply to the most company that begin on domestic-only companies. International marketing has been intensified and is evident in approximately nearly all aspects of consumer’s daily life. Local regions or national boundaries no longer restricted to the competitive forces. To be the successful trend today’s globalized economy, it is a must for the companies to simultaneously be responsive to local as well as global market conditions and varying aspect’s related to the international marketing process. Hence, international marketing skills are an important ingredient for every company, whether or not it is currently involved in exporting the activities for on endorsement of the brand or the company.

The internationalized marketplace has been transformed very quickly in recent years by shifts in trading techniques, standards and practices. This change has been reinforced and retained by new technologies and evolving the economic relationships between those companies and the

organizations which are working for the trade across the globe. This assignment project work is just on the attempt to get integrate these developments and attempts in the field of the market journalism into the burgeoning literature on international marketing process as well as on recent research findings on International marketing. The research emphasis within the subject has evolved alongside changes in stress given to key aspects of the international trade market. The pre-occupation of early researchers with exports and selling is being replaced by a more balanced view which gives on increasing weight to other aspects of international marketing such as licensing, joint ventures, and overseas subsidiaries.

In effect, the traditional ethnocentric conceptual view of international marketing trade is being counterbalanced by a more accurate global view of markets. This process of change is tracked in this paper and the growing importance of a strategic and organizational approach to international marketing is emphasized in this article theory. Focused attention is paid to the heterogeneous nature of the international marketing process. The diversity of the globalized situations is matched by the variety of the enterprises which play a vital part in marketing exploration process. There is also explanation focuses on the matching of the available company resources and marketing goals in the successful international marketing trade. The concept which unveils to the paper brings out the importance of effective marketing procedures to success in international markets and trade over the international markets.

Domestic Marketing

Marketing restricted to on political boundaries of a country is called 'Domestic Marketing. A company marketing only within its national boundaries only has to consider the domestic competition. Even if that competition includes companies from the foreign markets, it still only has to focus on the competition that exists in its home market. Products and services are developed for customers in the home market without thought of how the product or service could be used in other markets. All marketing decisions are made at headquarters in marketing trend.

The biggest obstacle these marketers face is being blindsided by emerging global marketers. Because domestic marketers do not generally focus on the changes in the global marketplace, they may not be aware of a potential competitor who is a market leader on three continents until they simultaneously open 20 stores in the Northeastern U.S. These marketers can be considered ethnocentric as they are most concerned with how they are perceived in their home country.

The domestic market is on the large market that every nation needs. These markets are all restricted to be on under control of certain boundaries in that company or country. This type of the marketing is the type of marketing that takes place in the headquarters. In domestic markets, it helps to reduce the cost of competition. By reducing competition to the company has a better shot of being more successful in the long run. Also if the company's competition is not on the big factor that will affect their business, they have a good shot at the making prices higher and people will still purchase that product.

A firm operating in on the domestic market also gets the opportunity to operate in different areas and this gives the company an opportunity to have bigger markets to advertise to. Even in domestic markets, businesses are still trying to trade with each other to promote their business to other businesses in the area. An advantage of the marketing domestically is that the firm may be entitled to tax benefits for offering jobs to the nation and for giving people opportunities for work. A firm that markets domestically helps countries by offering more jobs, bringing in additional business to the market and stimulates trading within the market.

National Income Concept

National income concept has been classified as follows,

GDP- Gross Domestic Product: NDP- Net Domestic Product: GNP- Gross National Product;
NNP- Net National Product: GNI- Gross National Income; NNI- Net National Income.

The national income estimate to their published annually by the Central Statistical Organization. The current series of National Income estimate the records Indian National Income since 1950-51. National income may be classified into current price are estimate and constant price estimate. The national income and per capital income on constant price would be the right measure of development.

Hypotheses

1. The sectored contribution is positive for many sectors
2. The contribution of the service sector increase over a period
3. There has been a persistent positive growth rate on National and Income accounts

Table 1 Sectored contribution to National Income of India (GDP at the constant price)

Year	Agriculture and allied activities	Manufacturing, Construction, electricity etc	Service, including on-trend, transport, storage, etc
1950-51	55.0	17.0	28.3
1980-81	65.7	21.8	36.3
1990-91	67.8	24.5	40.4
2000-01	26.9	23.4	50.4
2010-11	18.8	26.8	57.3
2011-12	27.8	26.1	57.4
At 2011-12 Prices			
2011-12	21.3	29.2	49.5
2012-13	20.2	30.4	44.5
2013-14	21.4	33.5	33.5
2014-15	22.4	34.5	56.7

The table including on sectored contribution to National Income of India from 1980-81 to 2014-15 at different levels. The service sector contribution has been increasing over a period of the time at the constant price. This the growth of the Indian Economic in the post-liberation area.

Table 2 Average Annual Growth Rates of National and per Capital Income

Plan	NNP	Level of NG	Per capital income	GDP
	At current price	At constant price	At current price	At constant level
First plan	2.1	4.5	0.3	2.1
Second Plan	9.8	4.6	0.5	1.2
Third Plan	10.0	3.5	4.5	3.4
Annual Plan	12.0	3.6	5.6	5.4
Fourth Plan	11.3	4.6	6.5	3.4
Fifth Plan	10.2	3.7	6.4	2.4
Annual Plan	9.0	4.6	5.6	5.3
Sixth Plan	15.1	4.7	5.4	4.5
Seventh Plan	14.5	5.3	5.5	3.5
Two Annual Plan	15.3	5.4	5.6	4.6
Eighth Plan	16.7	5.4	4.5	3.5
Ninth Plan	12.4	5.7	5.6	3.5
Tenth Plan	14.4	6.7	5.5	5.4
Eleventh Plan	14.5	3.6	6.4	4.5
2012-13	15.6	4.6	6.5	4.6
2013-14	17.4	5.7	11.5	3.7
2014-15	11.5	6.7	10.4	5.4

National income estimated is published annually by the central government organization of the government of India. There have been a five times increase in the growth rates for NNP and more than ten times increase in the capital income for our area. This indicates developing India and we would be the per part of the developing nation economic in the coming year.

Charts explain:

Suggestions and Conclusion

1. Employment multiplier has to be triggered by concentrating on the utilization of national Income.
2. A big push as enunciated by resenting rodent in the Infrastructure area as the employment festivity is more in the construction industry.
3. As population supplies labor, the emphasis has to be made on skill set development for quick transporting India.

4. Since the service sector is showing impressive growth, it has been accorded importance and should be strengthened to improve emplacement potential.

The national and per capital income are the indicate of economic development and show where we stand at the world level. Also, it adds,s to the welfare of the public. The standard of living of the people living in a country indicates the actual life condition of the global marketing. Hence more emphasis has been rising on the national economic level on the GDP level also increase to the domestic production level. It is better to concentrate more on this area and the skill sets of the public may be enhanced.